

Education Quarterly Reviews

Chen, J., Shen, H., & Hu, S. (2023). A Survey Study of a Catechism Course in Academic English Writing. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 6(3), 161-172.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.06.03.771

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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A Survey Study of a Catechism Course in Academic English Writing

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Abstract

This article conducted an investigation on the data associated with the academic English writing course offered through Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). This article was to gain initial insights into the development of the course. Employing a case study methodology. This article conducted a sample survey to evaluate students' perceptions of the course. Building upon these findings. This article undertook a comprehensive literature review and integrated the proposed teaching ideas of several experts to develop a MOOC teaching model for academic English writing. This article optimizes teaching strategies and enhances education and training programs across three key dimensions: universities, teachers and students, and the platform. By doing so, the overall quality of academic English writing instruction could be significantly improved.

Keywords: Catechism, Academic English Writing, MOOCs, Online Education

1. Introduction

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have revolutionized education by emphasizing the utilization of "micro-videos" or "micro-lessons" rather than traditional 45-minute online classrooms. In this format, each video is restricted to a maximum duration of 15 minutes. This approach facilitates focused attention from students and facilitates the breakdown of complex concepts, thereby enhancing learning effectiveness. With the reformation of the basic education curriculum, there has been a shift from passive "receptive learning" to more active and cooperative "inquiry-based learning." Supporters of "catechism" argue that this innovative teaching method promotes inquiry-based learning and represents a departure from the traditional classroom model. However, it is important to clarify that the "learning first" advocated by "catechism" does not align with the notion of "self-learning" in the context of the new curriculum reform. Rather, "learning first" entails students studying the textbook before receiving instruction from the teacher. This approach places significant emphasis on in-class self-study, followed by teacher-guided instructions based on students' individual progress. Current implementations of "catechism" involve a "listen first" approach, wherein students watch video lectures by teachers instead of studying the textbook at home or outside of class. The teacher breaks down key concepts and difficulties, providing specific analyses of texts and step-by-step solutions for example problems, while students engage in practice exercises.

Wang Qiuyue (2014) notes that this approach, although different from traditional receptive learning, remains essentially unchanged in terms of its core principles. In the past, students listened to teachers in the classroom, and now they listen to them at home, merely altering the time and location but not the fundamental nature of receptive learning. Furthermore, the inquiry-based learning promoted by the new curriculum reform seems to have regressed into receptive learning through the implementation of "catechism." It is crucial to recognize that "catechism" was originally designed as a means to assist absent students in catching up on missed classes, rather than as a preferred method of instruction for the majority of students. In developed countries, "catechism" is primarily employed in higher education for adult learners, rather than in basic education. The adoption of new technologies, such as "catechism," in primary and secondary education in Europe and the United States has been met with more caution than enthusiasm, reflecting a relatively conservative stance.

2. Literature Review

The landscape of MU education institutions comprises Coursera, edX, Udacity, Khan Academy, and Codecademy, which are primarily consortia or affiliated institutions of American universities. Among them, Coursera, edX, and Udacity are commonly referred to as the "troika" of catechism education. The emergence of these three major online education platforms has expanded the availability of systematic learning opportunities for diverse student populations. Although these "catechism" platforms operate on a non-profit basis, they have also embarked on some commercial endeavors. Leveraging the high-quality teaching resources of universities, they have created higher education courses, paving the way for a novel "learning at your fingertips" paradigm. Students not only gain unrestricted access to valuable resources but also have the ability to tailor their learning objectives using computer technologies, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of their educational pursuits (Zhang Kitesyuan, 2014).

Simultaneously, Chinese universities are establishing their own catechism platforms. Shanghai Jiao Tong University, in collaboration with Peking University, Tsinghua University, Fudan University, Zhejiang University, Nanjing University, University of Science and Technology of China, Harbin Institute of Technology, Xi'an Jiaotong University, and other esteemed C9 Chinese Ivy League universities, along with Tongji University, Dalian University of Technology, and Chongqing University, is building China's own "MU." According to President Zhang Jie of Shanghai Jiao Tong University, "The massive open online courses initiated in the United States have begun to fundamentally impact traditional higher education, leading to a restructuring of universities and ultimately shaping a new educational landscape" (Cao Jijun, 2013).

Gao's (2014) research on catechism teaching platforms reveals that over a dozen countries, including the United States, the United Kingdom, Japan, Australia, and China, are actively promoting the development of catechism, aspiring to expand their influence within the global education landscape. It is crucial to recognize that the impact of catechism extends beyond immediate changes in teaching methods; it also influences national development strategies concerning curricula, education, culture, and informationization. Therefore, it is imperative for governments, universities, and educators to acknowledge the profound influence of MU. The state should strengthen the top-level design of educational modernization from a strategic planning perspective, while educational institutions need to actively and effectively explore avenues to enhance the quality of talent development. Attention should be given to the following operational-level considerations to address the impact of catechism: (1) further promoting the concept of student-centered teaching, (2) establishing a robust teacher evaluation system based on scientific principles, and (3) enhancing the assessment system for teachers to ensure continuous improvement.

2.1 Researches on the development of catechism platforms

The concept of MOOCs was initially proposed by scholars at the University of Prince Edward Island and later gained recognition and adoption by esteemed American institutions such as Harvard University and Yale University. According to He Keqiang (2005), integrating traditional teacher-centered classroom teaching with student-centered online learning maximizes the advantages of both approaches, facilitating the attainment of educational objectives. In the context of China's higher education landscape, MOOCs possess the necessary conditions for teaching and learning, including courses designed by renowned scholars and the availability of

unrestricted access for students through online delivery formats. These factors effectively address some of the challenges faced by Chinese universities at the present stage of education.

2.2 Researches on academic English writing courses

The traditional academic English writing classroom heavily relies on in-person instruction. However, MU and MOOCs disrupt this conventional approach by providing an open, flexible, and cost-free learning environment, coupled with extensive learning resources. One key feature is the equitable distribution of teaching resources, which fosters efficient self-paced learning among students.

In contrast to the passive learning prevalent in Chinese compulsory education, MOOCs require and promote the development of students' goal-setting abilities, self-discipline, and timely completion of courses. This departure from and enhancement of traditional Chinese education not only exposes students to new knowledge but also cultivates essential learning skills (Xiaoling, 2023).

3. Data analysis of MOOC academic English writing courses

3.1 Analysis of the current situation of academic English writing courses offered on MOOC platforms

The availability of online learning resources in China dates back to the establishment of the Super Star online resource technology platform in 1993. However, with the introduction of the China University MOOC platform in 2014, the development of China's open online course platforms has experienced even greater growth and potential. Taking into consideration the data from the "Online Open Course Sharing Platform of Zhejiang Higher Education Institutions," it is evident that the platform has garnered significant attention. The platform currently boasts an impressive 3,416,261 online users, including 27,075 teachers. Collaborations with 633 universities have resulted in a total of 4,349 courses being offered, out of which 89 are classified as national quality courses, and 956 as provincial quality courses. Among the platform's course offerings, 89 are considered national-level boutique courses, while 956 are categorized as provincial-level boutique courses. The advent of MOOC platforms has transformed the landscape of education, expanding it beyond the confines of traditional face-to-face classroom interactions. Learners now have the opportunity to engage in flexible and self-paced learning experiences, accessible anytime and anywhere. Additionally, numerous universities, including esteemed institutions, have made their online course resources freely available, thus alleviating some of the financial burdens associated with education for students.

To explore the status of academic English writing courses across different MOOC platforms, the research team conducted an investigation and compiled the findings into a data graph (Figure 1). The graph indicates that academic English writing courses have witnessed widespread development on major MOOC platforms. Notably, "Youcuo," "China University MOOC," and the "Online Open Course Sharing Platform of Zhejiang Higher Education Institutions" offer a rich array of courses in this domain. These findings highlight the extensive growth of academic English writing courses on MOOC platforms.

Figure 1: Total number of academic English writing courses offered

3.2 Case data analysis of academic English writing courses on MOOC platforms

As a platform for learning and exchange, MOOC platforms inherently possess teaching feedback mechanisms. The star ratings, number of ratings, and viewership statistics of teaching courses serve as valuable indicators of course effectiveness and utility. In this study, the project team selected five courses from different universities through the China University MOOC platform and compiled relevant data to assess course quality (refer to Table 1). Additionally, the team extracted a representative sample of high and low-rated reviews to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the strengths and limitations of university students' learning experiences in MOOC academic English writing courses.

The survey data presented in Table 1 revealed that the average number of viewers for the selected courses exceeded 2000, indicating a substantial interest and demand among university students for academic English writing courses offered on MOOC platforms. Among the five courses, Academic English Writing by Southeast University not only garnered a significant number of viewers but also received a considerable number of evaluations, suggesting a notable level of feedback capability for that particular course. Furthermore, the fluctuating rating stars around 4.6 (out of 5) for the various types of academic English writing courses indicated a certain level of divergence in evaluations, adding valuable insights for course assessment. These findings lay the groundwork for the project team to conduct further surveys to evaluate the courses in greater detail.

Table 1: Top 5 English writing course evaluation data

Course Name	English Writing	Advanced English Writing	Writing English for Academic Purposes	Writing English for Academic Purposes (2)	General Academic English Writing
Number of viewers	2391	1596	7999	3085	589
Number of course evaluations	98	48	1010	390	32
Course Evaluation Star Rating	4.9	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.5
Host school	Wuhan University of Technology	Xi'an International Studies University	Southeastern University	Beijing University of Technology	China University of Political Science and Law

4. Evaluation analysis of MOOC academic English writing courses

This research aims to investigate the teaching evaluations of students in MOOC academic English writing through a sample survey, as well as analyze the learning records of university students enrolled in the course. By examining these two aspects, we can identify the deficiencies raised in students' evaluations and the progress observed in their learning records. As the MOOC format has a global reach, it is imperative for instructors to enhance their academic qualifications to ensure a certain level of rigor. In light of this, Zhang Xiufang (2005) proposes an approach where teaching materials are divided into smaller modules, allowing for a logical sequencing of the teaching process. By organizing the modules in a logical progression from superficial to in-depth content, students can systematically accomplish the behavioral objectives associated with each module. As MOOCs are online and offer flexibility, teachers should strategically structure their courses, ensuring a logical flow from basic to advanced concepts while allocating an appropriate amount of instructional time.

4.1 A sample of student evaluations of MOOC academic English writing courses

To ensure the generalizability of our study, our research team selected four courses from different universities on the MOOC platform (refer to Table 1). We randomly sampled student comments from each course, which allowed us to collect the following feedback on teaching effectiveness:

Course 1: Writing English for Academic Purposes

Student Comments:

- (1) The course content is concise and well-structured, with focused lessons that greatly enhance learning.
- (2) Teacher Liu is excellent, delivering clear lectures and providing ample class time. Deserves five stars!
- (3) The teacher is articulate and patiently addresses students' questions, imparting practical skills effectively.
- (4) The organization is clear, and there is an abundance of examples.
- (5) The course offers rich content, and the availability of materials in the online classroom allows for convenient access to valuable writing knowledge.

Course 2: Advanced Academic English Writing

Course Evaluation:

- (1) The class is highly practical, but the teacher's emphasis on theories and concepts is excessive.
- (2) The teacher's lectures were cut short.
- (3) The teacher provided detailed explanations, leading to significant learning outcomes.
- (4) The professor provided comprehensive analysis of English writing skills and strategies, covering various levels of detail.
- (5) The balanced ratio of Chinese to English usage during the course was comfortable, and I acquired substantial knowledge.

Course 3: Writing English for Academic Purposes

Course Evaluation:

- (1) I have gained valuable and practical knowledge that I can consistently apply in my future studies. The course is comprehensive, clear, and has made academic paper writing in English less daunting.
- (2) Studying the academic writing course at Beijing University of Chemical Technology has been highly beneficial.
- (4) Some of the Chinese translations are awkward and do not align with Chinese linguistic conventions. Some are outright incorrect, such as "eye and choppy" and "elevate vocabulary."

Course 4: General Academic English Writing

Course Evaluation:

- (1) This course provides a refreshing departure from the dry and insubstantial writing courses on MOOCs. The content and structure are rewarding. However, the teaching style is somewhat "old-fashioned," resembling outdated videotape courses. The course's strong content is hindered by the lecture style.

(2) I believe this course has tremendous potential, offering direct assistance in writing rather than imposing rigid templates. Nevertheless, there are noticeable drawbacks. The approach feels perfunctory in many aspects, making it difficult to follow the PowerPoint examples due to the teacher's obstruction. The running water effect in the PPT and mechanical reading add to the challenge. Despite these issues, the course remains valuable, providing significant guidance. I hope the teacher invests more thought into its delivery.

The aforementioned courses were offered by Wuhan University of Technology, Xi'an University of Foreign Studies, Southeast University, and China University of Political Science and Law. Analyzing the students' course evaluations, it is evident that the overall assessment of MOOC courses by students is positive. They have acquired knowledge and skills related to academic writing through self-directed study.

Simultaneously, the evaluations reveal areas for improvement in the courses, highlighting the need to enhance teaching models and move away from traditional methods. Although the universities excel in delivering cutting-edge content, their teaching approaches have yet to evolve. This comment underscores the importance of transforming MOOC teaching in China, as the current delivery lacks rigor and obscures the instructional content.

These findings demonstrate that China possesses cutting-edge knowledge and ideas. However, specialized training in innovative teaching methods is necessary to adapt to the online learning environment and achieve better results in MOOC delivery. Moreover, MOOCs challenge students' learning abilities, necessitating the development of critical discernment rather than passive acceptance of all information.

4.2 A case study of English majors taking a MOOC academic English writing course on their own

In this study, the project team selected the MOOC platform to investigate academic English writing. Specifically, they focused on the Academic English Writing course offered by Liaoning University over a two-month period. Remarkably, the team had the opportunity to observe the course's progress in real-time as it coincided with their research investigation. They actively participated in the complete MU academic English writing course and documented their learning experience through weekly journals.

Regarding course content, the lectures covered various aspects, including the definition of research, distinctions between quantitative and qualitative approaches, conducting research in both domains, academic writing principles, essay completion, appropriate academic writing style, effective punctuation usage, and academic essay formatting. The curriculum provided comprehensive and structured guidance, covering each step of the academic writing process. The students participating in the academic course were first-year students who had limited exposure to academic English writing. However, upon completing the course, they expressed having gained a preliminary understanding of academic English writing.

The teaching methods employed in MOOC academic English writing courses demonstrate a cutting-edge and innovative approach compared to traditional offline courses. For instance, the initial lessons introduced novel concepts like the "wheel research method" and the "classification research method," offering fresh perspectives on documentation. Subsequent lessons progressively delved deeper into ESP teaching, providing foundational knowledge for academic purposes. Additionally, the fourth lesson introduced the outstanding CNKI data search website and emphasized adherence to APA and MLA guidelines. The teaching approach aimed to present English academic writing from an international standpoint, offering students content with cross-regional relevance.

It is worth noting that the benefits of academic writing instruction through MOOC extend beyond theoretical knowledge acquisition. Students also experience cognitive development, enhanced critical thinking skills, and rigorous mental exercises. MOOCs provide a platform for nurturing students' intellectual capacities in addition to imparting practical writing skills.

5. The construction of a "catechism teaching model" for academic English writing

5.1 The concept of "catechism teaching model"

The popularity of major MOOC platforms stems from their convenience, which serves as a cornerstone for their widespread adoption. However, the lack of student-teacher interaction on these platforms poses a significant challenge. Students require targeted tutorials and clear study guides to overcome this obstacle. Hence, when designing a "MOOC teaching model" for academic English writing, it is essential to prioritize course relevance, prevent teaching homogeneity, and foster course refinement. This can be achieved by strengthening the sense of participation among students and teachers, establishing robust connections between the university, teachers, students, and the platform, thereby promoting the integrated and parallel development of these components.

In the reviewed literature, Xie Ping (2020) highlights the supportive role of the "three-loop" blended English teaching method in facilitating students' independent learning. Chen Jing (2021) emphasizes the impact of students' emotional and cognitive engagement on blended academic English writing courses. Additionally, Shang Yunhe (2022) suggests that guided learning videos can alleviate difficulties faced by university students in the learning process. Therefore, constructing a "blended model" should take into account the emotions and engagement of the main stakeholders. Moreover, incorporating appropriate amounts of introductory videos can enhance the flexibility of writing courses. In the Internet+ era, digital information accessibility enables the online and offline delivery of writing courses to coexist and develop in tandem.

5.2 Building the foundations of the "catechism" model

The initial step towards achieving effective collaboration between universities and catechism platforms involves establishing a robust linkage. Universities are responsible for providing qualified teachers and students, while the catechism platform primarily offers an AI-driven intelligent writing revision system, a grading system, an extensive library of teaching videos, and an online live teaching system. Building upon this collaboration, the university engages English writing teachers to instruct platform operations through the online platform, while in-classroom instruction by teachers focuses on equipping students with essential platform usage skills. Once these foundational elements are in place, further optimization and development of the course can be pursued.

5.2.1 Technical requirements for the "catechism" model

The "I write" English writing teaching platform offers an exemplary illustration of how an AI-driven essay revision system can significantly enhance students' grammar and spelling accuracy. With this system, teachers can focus on analyzing and guiding the structure and ideas within students' essays, thereby saving considerable time. Consequently, the integration of intelligent essay revision processes plays a vital role in establishing an effective "catechism teaching model."

One of the most notable features of the MOOC platform is its resource exchange function, enabling students to access relevant video libraries and teaching aids. This provision empowers students to learn at their convenience, irrespective of time and location.

To align more seamlessly with university teaching programs, implementing a booking system for public courses proves to be a valuable strategy. Such an approach not only fills gaps in the university's extracurricular schedule but also helps prevent scheduling conflicts within the regular curriculum.

5.2.2 The "catechism" teaching format

The Catechism model represents a blended approach to teaching that combines offline and online components. Offline teaching aims to foster interaction between teachers and students while providing opportunities for face-to-face engagement, enabling students to fulfill their study requirements and participate in classroom team activities. The university establishes a connection with the catechism platform and utilizes it to develop teaching

plans for instructors and learning objectives for students. Teachers collaborate with the platform by following the step-by-step plans and offering feedback upon completion.

Throughout the course, teachers utilize software tools provided by the institution's platform to supplement students' learning experience. They leverage videos and relevant literature to augment theoretical knowledge acquisition. Additionally, the platform's convenience allows for the assignment of homework tasks and facilitates academic interaction. Students, on the other hand, leverage the platform's AI revision function to identify simple grammatical and lexical errors in their essays. This process not only advances the course but also enhances their ability to self-assess and refine their writing skills. Moreover, students access relevant knowledge through the platform's corpus system, allowing them to internalize and assimilate the writing styles of others, thereby supporting their development in academic English writing.

Figure 1: An attempt to run a "catechism model" for academic English writing

5.3 The need for various aspects of the "catechism model"

5.3.1 The role of the platform

The catechism platform serves as a primary medium for online teaching and holds a pivotal position in the "catechism teaching model." Once the project is successfully launched, the platform should collaborate with contracted universities to develop a series of English academic writing courses aligned with relevant English major training programs. Additionally, ensuring a secure online environment throughout the course is crucial to prevent external interference. Upon course completion, the university should be notified, and with proper permission and accreditation, video resources and related literature should be published in the resources section of the platform. This facilitates the exchange of online course resources among universities, fostering comprehensive improvement in students' academic English writing skills. Technical support provided by the platform is equally essential. This includes features such as the "essay self-test" and an extensive library of videos and literature, which are challenging to replicate in physics teaching. Furthermore, the systematic assessment of initial writing submissions on the platform is vital as it significantly reduces the time required for teachers to provide essay corrections.

5.3.2 The role of universities

Catechism platforms heavily rely on universities as their primary providers. Consequently, it becomes crucial for universities to establish coherent teaching plans and objectives within the framework of the "catechism teaching model." English academic writing, being just one facet of English language learning, represents only a portion of the curriculum for English language students. Thus, optimizing the course's efficiency becomes a paramount goal. To achieve this, course tasks should be thoughtfully designed as periodic assignments, aiming to enhance students' writing skills and foster cognitive flexibility. Furthermore, it is imperative to establish appropriate academic targets that can serve as a source of motivation for both teachers and students throughout the course.

During the development of a training program, emphasis should be placed on achieving "refinement" and "targeting" to cater to the diverse needs of academic English writing. For instance, specific directions can be explored, such as writing in business and economics or writing in translation. This approach ensures a well-rounded curriculum that addresses students' varied interests and goals, ultimately maximizing efficiency. Furthermore, the program design should prioritize creating a conducive learning environment that fosters emotional engagement among students and teachers alike, as this has been shown to contribute to overall effectiveness.

By focusing on optimizing efficiency and effectiveness, universities can enhance the quality of English academic writing courses within the catechism platform. This approach not only serves the larger objectives of English language learning but also aligns with the multifaceted nature of students' academic journeys.

5.3.3 The role of teachers and students

Teachers and students play pivotal roles in the development of the MU teaching model. It is crucial for teachers to undergo training and gain proficiency in the new online teaching platform to minimize errors in the planning phase. During the teaching process, teachers should prioritize offline instruction while incorporating online teaching methods. This approach not only complements the limited interaction between teachers and students in online courses but also adds dynamism to the classroom, fostering empathy and emotional engagement. As a contemporary educational tool, the MU platform should be fully embraced by both teachers and students. Teachers should strive to share their teaching resources on the MU platform, while students should proactively take charge of their own learning, utilizing the platform's resources to overcome challenging problems and engaging in mechanical tests and extended writing exercises to enhance their skills. This approach reduces the burden on teachers for essay corrections, allowing them to focus on guiding students in developing coherent writing structures and ideas.

6. The benefits of the MU model for academic English writing for all parties

6.1 For colleges and universities

The Catechism mode of teaching academic English writing is a unique teaching mode for universities, which can improve the diversity of teaching in universities. Secondly, the MU platform provides universities with a network of information technology to help them, to a certain extent, equipped with powerful hardware equipment, providing a corresponding online teaching platform, which makes up for the lack of resources in some universities, the problem of tight teaching courses. In the preparation of English students in colleges and universities, it provides a variety of training routes and improves the teaching and training system of colleges and universities.

6.2 For teachers

The "catechism model" is still a new way of teaching for most modern teachers, so in terms of teaching methods, teachers gain new ways of teaching. In addition, teachers can also integrate their own teaching experience with online teaching methods, which in turn will lead to more teaching models and ideas. "The Catechism model is a pioneering and innovative approach. In the course, the teacher will be very different from the single offline teaching mode of the past, in which the teacher only reads the theory of writing in class and issues writing assignments at the end of class, which take most of the teacher's time to correct. Under the MU teaching model, students will be able to complete most of this content on their own, and the extra time saved will enable teachers to understand each student's writing style and shortcomings, and to provide targeted writing guidance to students, thus optimising the teacher's teaching mode and improving the overall standard of teaching.

6.3 For students

For students, the MU teaching model is a new way of teaching and learning. Unlike the old paper-based education, this teaching model allows students to go beyond the resources at hand. Students can search the platform's library

of open teaching resources from different universities, so that they can learn from the ideas of different schools even if they are at different universities, thus crossing the gap between different regions and universities, raising the upper limit of students' English academic writing resources, and achieving a breakthrough in students' self-reflection. Much of what is involved in this model is about the students' own self-awareness and emotional commitment to academic English writing, and what the teacher and platform can do to help is to generate interest in academic English writing, the benefits of which are positive feedback. Students will improve their academic English writing skills and broaden their access to learning resources as a direct result of the teaching model.

6.4 Platform-oriented

The most immediate advantage of a successful 'catechism model' for a catechism platform is that it brings momentum and fresh blood to the platform. A platform cannot be sustained without real people using and accessing it, so the platform may work with a number of universities to facilitate the sharing of resources between them. In completing the cooperation with major universities, the value of the platform itself has been sublimated. As a transit point for sharing academic resources, the platform itself will receive stronger technical support and first-class recruitment of interns, and while ensuring the normal operation of the platform, the platform and the universities will receive positive feedback on their interests, and the platform will improve its own fame and reputation through the on-campus publicity and dissemination of major universities, so as to attract more companies or universities in the society to negotiate and exchange with the platform, and the influence of the platform will grow further.

7. Summary and outlook

The MU teaching model for English academic writing represents an innovative approach aligned with the demands of the new era and the "Internet+" context. Its primary focus is on English undergraduate students seeking to enhance their skills in academic writing. The model aims to transfer essential course content to the classroom while utilizing the platform database for general theoretical information. This approach enhances course efficiency and provides students with comprehensive development opportunities across various domains. Furthermore, the applicability of the MU model extends beyond English academic writing to other English-related courses such as translation, listening, and speaking. Despite variations in course content, the effectiveness of the teaching model remains intact, warranting further investigation and exploration.

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Appendix

Table 2: Statistics

Platform Name	Total number of classes offered in English	Number of academic English writing courses offered	Total number of classes offered (university classes only)	Total number of platform users
UMOOCs	271	26	477	200000
CNKI Online Teaching	21	4	8910	
MOOC of Chinese universities	1320	62	9034	370000000
zhihuishu	475	30	10780	40000000
Xueyin Online Education	710	23	16800	47000000
UOOC	213	68	1377	500000
CNMOOC	49	19	3116	
ZJOOC	877	54	18658	3416261
CQOOC	110	10	522	